

Drones in docks and port areas to inspect ships and containers for radioactive material

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Abstract—In ports, containers are routinely inspected to detect illicit transport of nuclear material, due to, for instance, criminal activities or improper disposal of radioactive sources. Current inspection methods include sampling checks or passing the containers through a sensorized portal on the dock: all this can delay port activities and expose operators to danger. The ROSSINI project aims to reduce risk and promote early detections through unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs, or drones). Drones can deploy detectors close ships approaching the port, for initial screening. The system autonomously finds the containers using visual data. The drone path has to be optimized, given the battery constraints and the large number of containers on a ship. Our current work is to verify the project’s feasibility, performing tests with radiation sensors mounted on a drone approaching radiation sources of known characteristics. The drone position and the radiation levels are measured in real time, to see how the distance and any material (such as the metal sheets of which containers are built) between the source and the sensor influence the results. In the early tests we present here, we verified that a standard drone can carry the sensors we designed, and that the sensors are not disturbed by the flight conditions.

Index Terms—drones, docks, ports, radiations, inspections

I. INTRODUCTION

Intermodal or shipping containers are a key element of modern global logistics, used for the majority of goods trade by sea. In ports around the world, dedicated ships moving up to tens of thousands of “Twenty-foot Equivalent Units” (TEUs, after the standard size for such containers) are loaded and unloaded in docks. However, these containers can also carry dangers: for example, criminal groups may use them to hide undeclared or illicit materials. *Special Nuclear Material* (SNM) could thus be smuggled by terrorist groups or merely end up in ports due to reckless management of radioactive waste.

A famous case occurred in 2011 [1], when, during a routine inspection, Italian Firefighters in the port of Genova found an “orphan source” (namely, one whose origin could not be tracked) of ⁶⁰Co in a container filled with metal waste. Given the very high levels of radiation, the container had to be placed in an isolated area and cleared with an autonomous robot, for a total cost around a million euros, not to mention the health threat posed to operators and local residents.

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Figure 1. The system we trained finds the containers (a) in a satellite image of a dock, then extracts the waypoints and finds the optimal path (b).

Local laws and maritime regulations prescribe regular inspections of ships and containers to look for SNM. In most cases, a full inspection would be too slow, so only a few containers are checked. Common procedures are to send a human operator with a Geiger counter close to the containers, or to pass the latter through a land portal with sensors. Both these approaches are time-consuming, and the first one may also expose an unwitting operator to dangerous radiation levels.

The above shows the practical interest of a robotized inspection system [2]. Since containers are stored in large areas and piled in stacks tens of meters tall, drones seem a natural choice to carry sensors, as they can move close to the upper container layers and fly above obstacles. Thus, the ROSSINI (“Remotely-operated On-board inSpections for Special Nuclear materIal”) project was started: the first steps were to

- 1) *create* a tool that fetches a satellite image of a dock, then analyzes it to find the containers and the shortest path that passes above them, considering battery constraints;
- 2) *build* a sensor that is compact and lightweight, so it can be fit on a drone, and sensitive enough even from a distance;
- 3) *verify* that the sensor can work reliably during a flight.

II. CONTAINER RECOGNITION AND PATH PLANNING

While the drone flight can be set by the user, finding a path that inspects all containers is a tedious and non-trivial process. We thus reapplied ideas from previous work [3] on solar panels. These inspection tasks are similar, as we look for roughly rectangular structures (seen from above). We used

Figure 2. The Proto-0 (a) and Proto-1 (b) radiation source detectors.

project *PointRend* with *Detectron2*, a state-of-the-art platform for image segmentation (Fig. 1a) based on a *Neural Network*. The *OpenCV* library is also used, to define rectangles around the segmentation masks and then two waypoints W_i and W_j for each rectangle (at the midpoints of the short sides).

Moving from W_i to W_j ensures that the container is fully inspected. The second step is to find the shortest path through all containers: this is a special instance of the *Travelling Salesman Problem* (Fig. 1b) in which some edges (namely, those corresponding to a container) must be part of the path. In our system, we used both heuristic solvers from a standard Python library and exact solvers such as IBM CPLEX and Concorde; the former are much faster, while the latter always find an optimal solution, which we use as a reference.

III. SETUP

- *Drones*: we chose a Mavic 2 Enterprise Dual (“*Drone-0*”) and a Matrice 350 RTK (“*Drone-1*”), both by DJI.
- *Radiation sensors*: we used two detectors differing in weight, considering the drones’ *Maximum Take-Off Mass* (MTOM), and in measurement sensitivity. The main components are scintillating crystals; when a particle passes through them, they produce photons proportionally to the energy released. These crystals are ideal to get data about photons and neutrons emitted by SNM. “*Proto-0*” (Fig. 2a) is a prototype designed according to the CLEANDEM layout [4], with a $(1 \times 1 \times 1)$ cm³ BGO crystal. The weight is 200 g, within the MTOM of *Drone-0*. “*Proto-1*” (Fig. 2b) is an advanced design with a CsI scintillator crystal, encased in a box with plastic scintillator paddles, to isolate the signal from the background radiation; it weighs 2.3 kg, within the MTOM of *Drone-1*. The photons are detected by a matrix of silicon photomultipliers made by INFN-Ge. The DAQ is

based on Waveboard [5], a 250 MHz digitizer developed by INFN. The power supply is a rechargeable battery.

- *Radioactive sources*: to guarantee detection capability over a reasonably wide range of activities A , the detectors were tested and characterized using three radioactive sources provided by INFN-Ge, made of ¹³⁷Cs ($A = 3$ MBq), ²²Na ($A = 0.11$ MBq) and ²⁴¹Am ($A = 360$ MBq).
- *Position sensors*: both drones are equipped with GPS sensors, but these are unreliable in the tunnel where the tests took place, and their errors are comparable to the size of the inspection area S . Thus, we added in *Proto-0* an infrared position sensor, attached under the drone, whose coordinates are triangulated from three fixed “anchors” (base stations of known position, at the border of S).

IV. EXPERIMENTS

We compared the results from the detectors in our lab with those from GEMC simulations we developed [6]. Then we tested *Proto-0* during flight (on *Drone-0*), measuring the radiation from the three sources at different heights and distances within S : we thus obtained a map of A over S , as in [7]. The test results will be analyzed in a future paper.

V. CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORK

Preliminary tests show ROSSINI’s feasibility: we detected radiation sources from an aerial mobile robot. Future work includes testing the concept with *Proto-1* on *Drone-1*, to detect sources from larger distances. The path planning has been performed for 2D sets of waypoints, but container stacks are also vertically developed, thus a 3D path optimizer is necessary. The drone and sensor data will be sent to an online dashboard for real-time supervision. Finally, we will mount the detectors on quadruped ground robots, to be sent inside the containers if anomalous radiation levels are detected by the drone.

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